

ARTWIN

INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

NGPaas/SolAR wrapper to deploy SolAR components in NGPaaS micro services

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Executive Summary

The current document presents the tools to convert a computer vision pipeline developed with the SolAR framework and running in a stand-alone application into a service ready to deploy on the ARTwin cloud platform based on NGPaaS. The presented developments are part of the ARTwin project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. The main objective of ARTwin is to provide the European **industry and construction 4.0** with a sovereign **AR Cloud platform** that integrates a set of interactive technologies and services that meet their particular needs. In this respect, the services that are foreseen to be developed include:

- Development and updating of a **unified global map** of the factory/construction site;
- Real-time updating of a 3D **Digital Twin/BIM** of a factory/construction site;
- **Localization service** to track AR devices in order to assist workers in a factory or a construction site; and
- **AR remote rendering service** for displaying complex 3D models on low resources AR devices.

The document starts by presenting the **communication layer** aiming at offering easy data exchange between deployed services. This communication layer **based on gRPC** is developed as a feature of the **XPCF framework**, dependency of the SolAR framework managing configuration, injection, loading and introspection of component composing a SolAR vision pipeline.

Then, the document present developed tools to ease the **containerization of a SolAR service** into a **docker image**, and the perspective to extend the current features.

Finally, the current document concludes with a presentation of the perspectives for the **deployment, chaining and orchestration of SolAR based services together**, with a proof of concept evaluating the use of **ISTIO** to offer service chaining at the level of service instance in an asynchronous way.

1. Communication layer

The SOLAR Framework relies heavily on XPCF framework features (component configuration and injection, modules dynamic loading, interface introspection...).

As every SOLAR component is based on XPCF interface and component design, it permits to consider a common approach to automate the distribution of any XPCF component across the network (including SOLAR components), through its interfaces.

This approach has led to improve the XPCF framework to provide remote support from any XPCF interface declaration.

Current SOLAR pipeline runtime

Currently, the solar pipelines and samples are either mono or multithreaded stand-alone applications. A pipeline is a chain of components called from their interface (the interface serves as a contract between the application and the concrete implementation, and allows to change an implementation while using the same “service”).

Every component runs inside the same application/process on the same device.

Figure 1: SOLAR standalone application pipeline sample

Goal/purpose

The goal is to provide the ability to distribute the SolAR framework (either a single component, or meta-components such as pipelines) across the network with each part becoming a micro-service, such as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: SolAR distributed overview

Provided that interfaces only use serializable data structures (or base c++ types), XPCF provides all the tools needed for remoting code generation. Thus, any data structure defined by the SolAR framework can be exchanged between services deployed on the ARTwin cloud platform.

Architecture

Figure 3: XPCF remoting architecture

XPCF remoting architecture is based on XPCF encapsulation features.

Using XPCF component management feature, moving from a standalone application to a distributed application means to deduce a client component (also known as "proxy") and a server component both exposing the framework component interface implementation (-> a SolAR component interface in our use-case).

The proxy component forwards data and calls the service through a network remote procedure call library.

The server component is registered to the network remote procedure call library in the server application (xpcf_grpc_server).

The server component dispatches the calls to the original framework component implementation (-> a SolAR component implementation in our use-case).

Data serialization/deserialization is handled in both the proxy and the server components (the current implementation uses boost::serialization, other serialization options will be provided).

The current implementation uses grpc as its communication layer (and protobuf as the message layer). Any other communication/message layer could be used – support can be easily added to other backends in the xpcf_grpc_gen generation tool.

The proxy, server components and the grpc proto file are generated from XPCF interfaces.

The grpc service and stub are generated with the protoc compiler.

The generation tool (xpcf_grpc_gen) generates all the needed code around grpc and the qmake project file needed to build the remoting XPCF module, that will be used on both client and server sides.

Code generation

Figure 4: XPCF remoting code generation

(*) provided the interface follows a few

Interface guidelines

- A proxy and a server component are created for each interface
- Each proxy component implements a corresponding « business » interface (-> in our case a SolAR interface)
- « business » component (-> in our case a SolAR component implementation) is injected on the server side through its interface to the corresponding XPCF server component
- Server components inherit from `xpcf::IGrpcService`
- Code generation relies on a clang compilation database, generated from an IDE (QT Creator, VS using a plugin ...). It uses a forked version of `cppast` (with customization around templates parsing) and `libclang`.

Interface guidelines

An interface aiming to be supported by the automated remoting process must either:

- Use base c++ types only (STL containers are also supported)
- Use serializable data structures (data structures declaring and implementing one of the serialization methods available in XPCF specifications - boost serialization in XPCF 2.5.0)

Note: pointers are not handled.

- Anyway, as interfaces represent contracts between a user and a service, not handling pointers should not be an issue.

XPCF Remoting Domain Specific Language (DSL)

XPCF defines a Domain Specific Language to help remoting code generation in particular use cases.

The DSL is :

- Based on C++ user defined attributes
- Made to assist/extend the code generation
- Usable in XPCF Interfaces declarations

The DSL helps to:

- Remove ambiguities
- Maintain proxy and server components UUID stability
- Specify interfaces to ignore

In future releases: the DSL will allow to specify different remoting modes for methods (asynchronous, streaming ...)

DSL sample (DSL attributes have a grey background):

```
class [[ xpcf::clientUUID("fe931815-479c-4659-96c3-09074747796d") ]]  
[[ xpcf::serverUUID("2ee889a4-bb14-46a0-b6e9-a391f61e4ad0") ]]  
IMessage:    virtual public org::bcom::xpcf::IComponentIntrospect {  
    public:  
        virtual ~IMessage() = default;  
        virtual void display(std::string [[xpcf::in]] message) = 0;  
};
```

Runtime behavior

Initialization phase

Figure 5: XPCF remoting runtime behavior – initialization

Client side	Server side
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Configure proxies channel url 2. Inject remoting proxies to interfaces 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Configure server channel url and start server 2. Inject client components from modules to XPCF remoting server components thanks to their framework interfaces 3. Inject XPCF remoting server components as IGrpcService services 4. Register every IGrpcService to grpc

Runtime phase:

Figure 6: XPCF remoting runtime behavior – run overview

Client side	Server side
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Client calls a service through its interface 2. The interface is bound to the XPCF generated remoting proxy component: the service is called on the proxy and forwarded to grpc 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Listen to every IGrpcService registered 4. Forward calls from grpc server interface to XPCF Framework interface and to the concrete component bound to the interface

XPCF remoting tools

- xpcf_grpc_gen: Remoting code generation tool
- xpcf_grpc_server: Xpcf grpc server application to host any remoted service. Relies on IGrpcService interface from xpcf framework

Process to convert any framework from standalone to remoting

- Generate compilation database from the framework project
- Generate code from framework interfaces
- Build the generated XPCF remoting Module for the framework
- Adapt client and server configurations with needed services
- Launch xpcf_grpc_server application with the server configuration file and the modules

2. Containerization

XPCF grpc application

XPCF provides a server application named “xpcf_grpc_server” to host any IGrpcService server side component.

The “xpcf_grpc_server” application features are described below.

xpcf_grpc_server

The xpcf_grpc_server is an XPCF application. It hosts any IGrpcService enabled component and registers every xpcf IGrpcService component to grpc. Finally, the xpcf_grpc_server runs grpc server on the provided url and credentials (either with a configuration parameter or through the environment variable XPCF_GRPC_SERVER_URL and XPCF_GRPC_CHANNEL_CREDENTIALS). Without configuration, the server listens to "0.0.0.0:50051" with “insecure” channel credentials.

Note: the xpcf_grpc_server application is always the same, whatever the framework interfaces and the components used on the server side.

Container deployment

The deployment of the remoted application also benefits from XPCF features.

Hence the deployment :

- is configuration based
- allows to have a single Docker container definition for different component deployment declarations

is based on automated modules bundling using remaken - a meta dependencies management tool which supports different package formats (<https://github.com/b-com-software-basis/remaken> -

- Remaken dependency management).

In order to deploy any remoted components, three elements must be provided to the `xpcf_grpc_server` application:

- the XPCF configuration file with:
 - IGrpcService list of components,
 - The concrete modules declarations and configurations,
- the remoting framework module which provides the server side stubs which implement the `grpc` interfaces and will receive through injection the concrete framework implementations,
- the concrete modules (hosting the components that will be injected in the server side stubs).

Remaken dependency management

The SolAR framework is using the meta dependencies management tool **Remaken** that is developed by b<>com under Apache v2 license.

Figure 7: Remaken dependency management tool

As shown on Figure 7, Remaken is a meta dependencies management tool which supports different package formats, some cross platforms (Conan, vcpkg, Remaken based on pkg-config), and other dedicated to a given system (apt-get, pacman, yum, zypper, pkg, pkgutils, brew, chocolatey).

Remaken uses a *packagedependencies.txt* file defining all dependencies of a project. Thus, by maintaining a simple dependency file describing the third parties used by a project, it facilitates the generation of binaries bundle from a SolAR service.

The bundle can then be easily deployed to a container (e.g. Docker image).

3. Foreseen features & improvements

Use cases

- The previous use case can be extended: as the remoting code is hosted in a single module, a server can also be a client of another server and so on
- Extend sample use cases

Tools

Xpcf_grpc_gen:

- Enhance serialization methods support
- Enhance DSL to specify different remoting modes for methods (asynchronous, streaming ...)
- Flatbuffer messages support
- Improve c++ code parsing (class template specialization ...) [cppast]

xpcf_grpc_linter :

- Compile time tool
- Could validate XPCF remoting DSL attributes used
- Could validate interfaces data structures serialization support

4. Perspectives for orchestration

ISTIO based service chaining proof of concept

POC description and requirements

This proof of concept aims at validating the particular requirements to chain AR cloud services. Figure 8 shows an example of service deployment and chaining planned for the implementation of pilot use cases of the ARTwin project. This simple service architecture consists of the three following services deployed on the ARTwin platform:

- 3D sparse mapping service: This service creates a 3D local sparse map of the real environment observed by the vision sensors embedded in a single AR Device. It will receive images and corresponding poses estimated by AR runtime running on a given AR device, potentially at a frequency of 60Hz. The current map will be transmitted to the map update service at a lower frequency (every 1 to 10 seconds). This service is not fully resilient, and must preserve a context specific to the AR device it serves.
- Map update service: This service will receive 3D local sparse maps created by each 3D sparse mapping service instance dedicated to a given AR device. This 3D local map, built from fresh observations, will be merged in the global map managed by the map update service. As several global maps can be created for covering a very large area, a map update service instance will be dedicated to a single global map.
- Relocalization service: This service will receive an image from a dedicated AR device. It will also extract a part of the global map of interest according to the localization of the AR device. From the

requested image, and thanks to the 3D map representing the surrounding area of the AR device, the service will estimate the pose of the AR device in relation to the reference coordinate system of the map. Depending on implementation and deployment choices, the extraction of the local map from the global map stored on the Map Update Service can be done at a lower frequency than the AR device relocalization process. In this case, the local map extracted from the global map will be stored by the relocalization service implementation, and will be dedicated to a given AR device. Thus, a relocalization service instantiation will be deployed per AR device, and will handle only one AR device.

Figure 8: Example of service deployment and chaining for the AR cloud platform.

As service instantiations can handle a specific context (related to a given AR device or to a given global map), chaining must be defined at the service instantiation level (pods) and not only at the service level. For this purpose, we plan to use UID per AR device and map managed on the ARTwin platform, and to use these UIDs to chain service instances together. Note that all these services are asynchronous.

The objective of this proof of concept consists of evaluating if the features offered by ISTIO are able to tackle this chaining requirement at pod level in an asynchronous way.

POC installation

To rebuild the pipeline Go app, run this:

```
cd grpc
protoc --go_out=artwin --go_opt=paths=source_relative \
  --go-grpc_out=artwin --go-grpc_opt=paths=source_relative \
  artwin.proto
cd -
```

How to (re)build the Docker image

```
cd grpc
docker build -t grpc_program .
```

```
cd -
```

How to run GRPC applications with docker-compose

```
docker-compose up | down
```

How to configure and run the GRPC application

This is a basic GRPC program that can receive and send messages.

It supports three modes of operation:

- **client**: sending a message to a server or a relay
- **server**: listen for messages from a client or a relay
- **relay**: listen for message from a client, and retransmit this message to another server (either a relay or a simple server)

Deploy *relay* and *server* GRPC app into a k8s cluster

- Create the namespace named *artwin*:

```
kubectl apply -f namespace.yaml
```

- Create secret for b-com docker registry:

```
kubectl -n artwin create secret docker-registry regcred \  
  --docker-server=supra-docker-local.repository.b-com.com \  
  --docker-username=<your-name> \  
  --docker-password=<your-password> \  
  --docker-email=<your-email>
```

- Deploy the AR services:

```
kubectl apply -f 3d-sparse-mapping.yaml  
kubectl apply -f relocation.yaml  
kubectl apply -f map-update.yaml
```

- Deploy ISTIO resources:

```
kubectl apply -f istio/
```

Run the GRPC app as a *client*

```
docker run -it --network="host" \  
  -e APP_MODE="client" \  
  -e CLIENT_DEVICE_ID="<your-device-id>" \  
  -e CLIENT_DEST_EP="host:port" \  
  -e CLIENT_MESSAGE="I'm a GRPC client!"
```

grpc_program

host is the k8s public IP of the cluster (the API server IP). *port* is the listening port of the ISTIO ingress gateway. You can get it by running this command:

```
$ kubectl -n istio-system get service -o=custom-
columns=NAME:.metadata.name,PORT_NAME:.spec.ports [1].name,PORT:.spec.ports [1].port,NODE
_PORT:.spec.ports [1].nodePort
NAME                PORT_NAME  PORT   NODE_PORT
istio-egressgateway https      443    <none>
istio-ingressgateway http2      80     31636
istiod               https-dns  15012  <none>
```

Here the listening port is the *http2* nodePort 31636.

Check the deployment

The Figure 9 describes the different k8s resources deployed for this POC.

Figure 9: Kubernetes resources for POC implementation

The first deployed resource is an ISTIO [gateway](#) that describes a load balancer operating at the edge of the mesh receiving incoming or outgoing HTTP/TCP connections.

```
$ k -n artwin get gateway
NAME          AGE
ar-gateway    64d
```

A [ISTIO virtual service](#) can then be bound to a gateway to control the forwarding of traffic arriving at a particular host/service or gateway port. The *to-sparse-mapping* VirtualService resource will forward incoming HTTP traffic, i.e. GRPC requests, to a destination defined by the *sparse-mapping* DestinationRule resource.

The other VirtualService deployed resources define the chaining of the other AR services inside the cluster. The *to-relocalization* VirtualService resource specifies the forwarding of HTTP requests coming from any pod with a label *app* set to *sparse-mapping* to the service named *relocalization*. The *to-map-update* VirtualService resource specifies the forwarding of HTTP requests coming from any pod with a label *app* set to *relocalization* to the service named *map-udpate*.

Note that GRPC requests must be sent by *relay* pods to the mocked service named *ar-pipeline-1*. VirtualService rules are applied only to GRPC requests sent to this mocked service. There is none pods attached to this service. It's just a simple trick to define routing rules using internal known k8s FQDN name.

```
$ k -n artwin get vs
NAME          GATEWAYS          HOSTS          AGE
to-sparse-mapping  ["ar-gateway"]  ["*"]          27h
to-map-update      ["ar-pipeline-1"] 26h
to-relocalization ["ar-pipeline-1"] 26h
```

[DestinationRule](#) resources defines policies that apply to traffic intended for a service after routing has occurred. We specify a destination rule for each AR k8s service, to load balance incoming GRPC requests to attached pods. The [Consistent Hash-based](#) declared in rule load balancing is used to provide a soft session affinity based on the HTTP header X-Device-ID. **All GRPC requests sent a by a device will be handled by the same pod in the different AR services.**

```
$ k -n artwin get dr
NAME          HOST          AGE
map-update    map-update    19d
relocalization relocalization 19d
sparse-mapping sparse-mapping 19d
```

3 different AR services are deployed.

```
$ k -n artwin get svc
NAME          TYPE          CLUSTER-IP    EXTERNAL-IP    PORT(S)    AGE
ar-pipeline-1 ClusterIP     10.107.147.58 <none>         9000/TCP   69m
map-update    ClusterIP     10.97.157.151 <none>         9000/TCP   64d
relocalization ClusterIP     10.106.43.53  <none>         9000/TCP   64d
sparse-mapping ClusterIP     10.96.150.198 <none>         9000/TCP   64d
```

3 pods per service are deployed:

```
$ k -n artwin get pod
NAME          READY  STATUS  RESTARTS  AGE
```

map-update-5cf44997db-5n7pm	2/2	Running	0	27h
map-update-5cf44997db-tlgwg	2/2	Running	0	24h
map-update-5cf44997db-xqwkn	2/2	Running	0	24h
relocalization-7ddd9c6cf8-c7hk9	2/2	Running	0	24h
relocalization-7ddd9c6cf8-m4sbd	2/2	Running	0	24h
relocalization-7ddd9c6cf8-t5gdp	2/2	Running	0	24h
sparse-mapping-6b89854ccd-4gppl	2/2	Running	0	24h
sparse-mapping-6b89854ccd-rsbk6	2/2	Running	0	24h
sparse-mapping-6b89854ccd-zgk4h	2/2	Running	0	24h

The **Error! Reference source not found.** describes an example of invocation of the AR service chaining from 2 AR devices, thanks to ISTIO features.

Figure 10: Service chaining based on ISTIO for POC implementation.

Conclusion on POC

The proof of concept has demonstrated that ISTIO is able to meet the chaining requirements defined for the pilot use cases planned for the ARTwin platform. ISTIO is able to handle service chaining at the pod level to ensure that service instantiations dedicated to a given AR device can be chained together and that the services instantiation can run in an asynchronous way.

Integration to NGPaaS

Figure 11: SolAR Pipeline Deployment Integration with NGPaaS

The deployment described earlier consists of multiple steps and requires several commands to be entered at the command line. This operation is cumbersome, time consuming and error prone. NGPaaS allows to replace the manual commands with a one click that automates all the deployment steps.

The integration begins by wrapping each individual component (e.g. 3D sparse mapping service, relocalization service, etc.) in an RFB. The RFB contains the service function itself, its configuration files, and a playbook that automates the deployment and deletion of the component. Then, using tools from NGPaaS, we compose the different RFBs in a graph (tree to be accurate) that looks like the one in Figure 11 to create an end-to-end service blueprint that represents the SolAR pipeline composition. The customization of each component as well as the end-to-end service is done using metadata parameters that can be accessed on the same Web UI page instead of going through individual files. With one click the service and all its components are then deployed and this will produce the same result described in the previous section.

Another advantage of this method is the decoupling of the components from the execution environment where they are intended to run. Specifying the execution environment via the metadata reduces further the administration and deployment time, for it is not needed to log into each host and run the commands. Moreover, changing the execution environment of the service is a matter of updating the value of a variable in the metadata.

In the next iteration, we plan to eliminate the utilization of *Istio* to perform the service chaining and replace it with a built-in feature natively provided by NGPaaS technology.

The full implementation is planned in the second part of this Task 3.2, and the documentation will be available in deliverable D3.4 planned at M30.

5. Conclusions

We have presented in the current document the mechanisms developed to transform a SolAR pipeline into a service ready to deploy on the NGPaaS platform. Tools to automatically create a gRPC based communication layer for SolAR component interfaces and to ease the containerization of SolAR services into docker images have been implemented. A proof of concept has validated the use of ISTIO to handle the chaining of asynchronous service at the level of pods (service instances).

Several improvements are planned for the second part of this Task 3.2. First, a service deployment on the NGPaaS platform based on services developed in work package 4 have to be tested. Then, containerization automation has to be improved, and the service chaining will be replaced by a built-in feature natively provided by NGPaaS platform. Finally, some Service Level Agreements will have to be defined for SolAR based services in order to automate and optimize the distribution of services on the available infrastructure.

6. Appendix A: Glossary

Framework : interfaces collection with their datastructures

Concrete component/implementation : a component that implement one or several interfaces from a framework. It contains the code used when the application invoke an interface assuming the component is bound to this interface.